

1 **Transporter composition alterations during lineage commitment in pluripotent stem cells.**

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6 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
7 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here identification and
8 characterization of key changes in transporter composition during lineage commitment in embryonic stem
9 cells of the human embryo. Transporter composition alteration during lineage commitment in pluripotent
10 stem cells alluded to basic changes in ionic context associated with pluripotency and nutritional
11 requirements in the trophectoderm.

12 Citations

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17 trophectoderm of the mouse blastocyst. *Developmental biology*, 189(1), pp.148-160.